

Complexes of manganese(III) and cobalt(III) with some salicylidene-4,4-disubstituted-3-thiosemicarbazides

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Manuscript received 31 May 2000, revised 26 December 2002, accepted 13 February 2003

Complexes of Mn^{III} and Co^{III} with salicylidene-4,4-dimethyl-3-thiosemicarbazide (H₂saldmtsc), salicylidene morpholine-*N*-thiohydrazine (H₂salmth) and salicylidene piperidine-*N*-thiohydrazide (H₂salpht) of the types [MnL(LH)] and [Co₂L₃].*n*H₂O (H₂L = H₂saldmtsc, H₂salmth or H₂salpht and *n* = 1 or 3) have been prepared. The cobalt(III) complexes have been suggested to have low-spin dinuclear octahedral and the manganese(III) complexes high-spin octahedral structure.

The complexes of thiosemicarbazides and their thiosemicarbazones have been reported in literature¹. It has been found that thiosemicarbazone derivatives of salicylaldehyde form bis-ligated complexes with bivalent metal ions and usually stabilize the oxidation state (+2) under normal conditions². We report here the preparation and characterization of Co^{III} and Mn^{III} complexes with three thiosemicarbazone derivatives, viz. salicylidene-4,4-dimethylthiosemicarbazide (H₂saldmtsc) (A), salicylidene morpholine-*N*-thiohydrazide

(A)

(H₂salmth) (B) and salicylidene piperidine-*N*-thiohydrazide (H₂salpht) (C).

(B) X = O

(C) X = CH₂

Results and discussion

The compositional studies indicate that the ligands form complexes of types MnL(HL) and Co₂L₃.*n*H₂O (where, H₂L = H₂salmth, H₂salpht or H₂saldmtsc and *n* = 3 or 1) (Table 1). The complexes containing these metal ions in the bivalent state could not be isolated employing these ligands in

Compd.**	Decomp. temp., °C	Metal % : Found (calcd.)
Co ₂ L ₃ .3H ₂ O	260	12.54 (12.22)
Co ₂ L' ₃ .3H ₂ O	242	13.25 (13.04)
Co ₂ L'' ₃ .3H ₂ O	273	15.56 (15.06)
Mn(HL)L	190	10.03 (9.48)
Mn(HL')L'	178	9.20 (9.48)
Mn(HL'')L''	193	11.45 (11.02)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.
**H₂salmth = H₂L; H₂salpht = H₂L' and H₂saldmtsc = H₂L''.

atmosphere, which indicates that electron-donating alkyl substitution on the N⁴ atom probably enables the stabilization of oxidation state +3 of Mn and Co over the +2 state. The Mn^{III} complexes are slightly soluble in ethanol but insoluble in water. The Co^{III} complexes are insoluble in water and ethanol as well. However, these complexes are fairly soluble in dioxane and DMF. The DMF solution of the complexes are almost non-conducting indicating their non-ionic nature. The hydrated nature of the Co^{III} complexes, viz. Co₂L₃.*n*H₂O (*n* = 2 or 3) is adjudged from the loss of water molecules below 100° in the thermograms suggesting uncoordinated nature of H₂O in these complexes. The Co^{III} complexes display magnetic moment values (0.79–1.26 B.M.) corresponding to oxidation state +3 of cobalt and the observed paramagnetic value is attributed to low-spin state of the compound³. The magnetic moments of the Mn^{III} complexes, viz. Mn(HL)L (4.48–4.83 B.M.) suggest the oxidation state of +3 for manganese in these complexes⁴. The solid state reflectance spectra of the Co^{III} complexes, viz.

$\text{Co}_2\text{L}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ display a weak band or shoulder in the visible region at $17800\text{--}18520\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ transition in low-spin octahedral field^{3,5}. The band at $22220\text{--}22720\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to C.T. and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ transition. The Mn^{III} complexes display a shoulder or weak band at $15380\text{--}16130\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is assigned to ${}^5E_g \rightarrow {}^5T_{2g}$ transition in an octahedral field⁶. The band in the higher energy region ($25000\text{--}22730\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is tentatively assigned to C.T. transitions.

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectra of the ligand display ν_{NH} and ν_{OH} bands at $3310\text{--}3070\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which vanish completely in the Co^{III} complexes, but a weak broad band appears at 3270 cm^{-1} in the Mn^{III} complexes $\text{Mn}(\text{HL})\text{L}$. The complete disappearance of thioamide NH and OH stretches of the ligands suggests that both NH and OH hydrogens are deprotonated⁷ in the Co^{III} complexes, but at least one N-H proton of the coordinated ligand is retained in the Mn^{III} complexes, viz. $\text{Mn}(\text{HL})\text{L}$. A broad band appears at $\sim 3420 \pm 20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\text{Co}_2\text{L}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which is absent in $\text{Mn}(\text{HL})\text{L}$ due to the water molecule. The ν_{OH} bending of the ligands assigned to a band at $\sim 1390\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is absent in almost all the complexes, supporting the deprotonation of phenolic hydroxyl on complexation⁸. The $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band of the ligand is raised to higher frequencies in the complexes, which suggests that bond order of phenolic C-O is raised on coordination as usually observed for deprotonated phenolic C-O in Schiff base complexes of salicylaldehyde⁹. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band of the ligand located at $1624\text{--}1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is shifted to lower frequencies by $14\text{--}25\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes, suggesting the involvement of C=N nitrogen in bond formation⁹. The thioamide bands I, II and III of the ligands are shifted to higher frequencies while thioamide band-IV suffers a red shift, suggesting the involvement of thioamide sulfur atom in coordination^{10,11}. In case of the Mn^{III} complexes thioamide band-IV is located at two different positions, since one of the thioamide HNCS is deprotonated and the other is not deprotonated. From shift of thioamide band-IV to lower vibration it is inferred that thioamide HNCS proton is deprotonated in thiol form¹¹. Thus from IR characteristics of complexes it is inferred that these ligands are bonded to metal atom as a tridentate N, S and O donor molecule. A large red-shift of $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ band in the Co^{III} complexes indicates that 'S' is the bridging atom and the Co^{III} complexes $\text{Co}_2\text{L}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are probably dimeric. The new bands located in far-IR region at $600\text{--}450$ and $400\text{--}310\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are tentatively assigned to M-O and M-N stretches and these vibrations occur in the range of reported values^{11,12}.

Thus from the results it is suggested that metals are

present in oxidation state (III) in which Mn^{III} has high-spin mononuclear and Co^{III} has low-spin dinuclear octahedral structures.

Experimental

Preparation of ligands : Salicylidenemorpholine-*N*-thiohydrazide (H_2salmth), salicylidenepiperidine-*N*-thiohydrazide (H_2salpht) and salicylidene-4,4-dimethyl-1,3-thiosemicarbazide ($\text{H}_2\text{saldmtsc}$) were prepared by refluxing 1 : 1 molar proportion of the respective thiohydrazide or thiosemicarbazide with salicylaldehyde in methanol. The products were crystallized from methanol and analyzed.

Preparation of complexes $\text{Mn}(\text{HL})\text{L}$ and $\text{Co}_2\text{L}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{H}_2\text{L} = \text{H}_2\text{salmth}$, H_2salpht or $\text{H}_2\text{saldmtsc}$ and $n = 1$ or 3) : Hot methanol solution of the ligand (2 mmol in 40 ml) and metal acetate (1 mmol in 50 ml) were mixed. The pH of the resulting solution was raised by adding an aqueous methanolic solution of sodium acetate (2–3 g in 20–25 ml). The reaction mixture was then refluxed for ~ 0.5 h on a steam-bath, then kept at room temperature overnight when dark brown precipitate separated out either on standing or on diluting it with equal volume of cold water. The product was washed with aqueous methanol and dried over CaCl_2 .

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Hilger-Watt H-800 spectrophotometer and solid reflectance spectra on a Beckman DU-500 spectrophotometer.

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